

Inner speech vs. anendophasia: Eavesdropping our own minds and the question of information

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An article by Gregory in *The Conversation* in early 2024 re-introduced the inner speech experiences and referred readers to a 2023 publication by Nedergaard and Lupyan in 2023 [1-2]. Nedergaard and Lupyan's paper has proposed the term "anendophasia," describing the phenomenon whereby some people have not experienced inner speech [2].

Illustration: Eavesdropping our own minds. Generated by Google Bard AI.

Both the scicomm article and the scientific publication are thought-provoking and intriguing. They doubtless provide useful discussions and insights.

While reading both, I noticed one thing and thought about something useful for opening up an ensuing debate concerning the research problem.

First, I noticed that none of the articles contained the word of critical importance: information. They did not even use (in a major way) the word “thinking”.

Second, I thought of our information-processing paradigm for both theoretical reasoning and applied analytics [3-4]. It is pretty clear that inner speech and anendophasia may represent the ebb and flow of thinking or information processing within the mind.

Is it possible that anendophasia is related to the state of unpreparedness of the mind facing the incoming flow of information, causing an ebb? Maybe in certain circumstances, such as facing dangers (given enough time for information processing), the inner speech will switch on?

If that is the case, nature has a critical role to play in addressing this problem.

References

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[2] Nedergaard J, Lupyan G. (2023). Not Everyone Has an Inner Voice: Behavioral Consequences of Anendophasia. In: M Goldwater, FK Anggoro, BK Hayes, DC Ong (Eds.) *Proceedings of the 45th Annual Conference of the Cognitive Science Society* (pp.617-624). <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/93p4r8td>

[3] Vuong QH. (2023). *Mindsponge Theory*. Walter de Gruyter GmbH.

[4] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH, La VP. (2022). *The mindsponge and BMF analytics for innovative thinking in social sciences and humanities*. Walter de Gruyter GmbH.

